

Social Factors and Youth Restiveness in Southwest, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the social factors responsible for youth restiveness in Southwest, Nigeria. The descriptive research design was adopted for the study. All the youths between 16 and 35 years in Southwest, Nigeria constituted the population for the study. Multistage sampling procedure was used to select 1166 youths as sample for this study. A questionnaire tagged "Questionnaire on Social Factors and Youth Restiveness" (QSFYR) was used to collect the data. The face and content validity of the instrument were ascertained by experts in Social Studies, Texts, Measurement and Evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was done by using Cronbach Alpha reliability testing method. Overall of 0.96 reliability co-efficient was obtained and it is considered appropriate for this study. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to test all the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings from the study showed that there were significance relationships between leadership, peer influence, social media, and state of security except religion and youth restiveness in Southwest zone of Nigeria. It is hereby recommended that leaders at various levels should lead in accordance with moral principles and avoid acts capable of creating problems in allocation and distribution of resources and positions. Parents and guidance are advised to give their children proper orientation on the essence of chosen peer that will not influence or lure them into adopting negative behaviour in the society. Government at various levels and the security agents are also encouraged to sincerely tackle insecurity in the Southwest zone and Nigeria as a whole.

Keywords:

Leadership, Peer Influence, Social Media, Security, Religion.

Introduction

Peace is very important to human life and the general society so as to co-exist and enjoy expected development. Hence, hostility can hinder the needed peace and sustainable development in the society. However, in the recent time, it is observed that, the Southwest zone in Nigeria has witnessed a lot of hostility and chaos. The youths who are majorly between sixteen and thirty-five years in the zone have expressed several psychological, emotional and physical actions tending to lack of peace through demonstration, protest or unrest. The actions which are termed youth restiveness include anxiety, anger, worry, frustration, dissatisfactions, tension, vandalism and agitation. Youth restiveness therefore, is a violent expression of anger, worry, disappointment, grievance or dissatisfaction which the youths demonstrate in a bid to enforce demands on constituted institution(s). According to Mba, Ihejirika and Deckor (2021), youth restiveness is a form of agitation which the youths embark on in different communities in Nigeria. Some of the assumed factors to have triggered youth restiveness in Southwest zone of Nigeria include some social factors like leadership, peer influence, social media, drug abuse, religion and state of security.

In the recent time the leadership approach in Nigeria may have connection with youth restiveness in Southwest, Nigeria. when there is favourable leadership approach, citizens may conduct themselves peacefully with maximum cooperation with leaders in the society while unfavourable leadership approach may lead to revolt or restiveness especially among the youths. For instance, a study conducted by Tambawal and Sa'idu (2012) on causes of youth restiveness in Kano, northern part of Nigeria revealed that 98.4% (372) of the respondents believed that youth restiveness is caused by the poor leadership

approach in the northern part of Nigeria. Also, Mba, Ihejirika and Deekor (2021) carried out a study on whether leadership influences youth restiveness in Andoni and Opobo/Nkoro Local Government Areas of Rivers State, the study revealed that restiveness is caused by poor leadership in Andoni and Opobo/Nkoro Local Government Areas of Rivers State. Similarly, according to Ugwu-Nwogo (2021), youth restiveness has been attributed to leadership problem in Nigeria.

Furthermore, youth restiveness may have connection with peer influence in Southwest, Nigeria. Apart from home, peer group is another agent that inculcates behaviour into individuals, whether positively or negatively. According to Suleiman (2019), the influence of peer cannot be underestimated in relationship with youth restiveness. In determining whether peer influences youth restiveness, Uriah, Egbezor and Ololube (2014) carried out a research on the challenges that youth restiveness posed on educational development in Rivers State, respondents agreed with mean of 3.1345 and standard deviation .62756 that youths motivate themselves to restive. Similarly, Zambuwa (2022), found that youth restiveness is motivated by peer influence.

Another factor that could have strong relationship with youth restiveness in Southwest Nigeria is the social media. According to Ezeji (2020) many youths spread misinformation capable of creating incitement and violent reactions. More also, Abraham (2023) stated that many youths usually commit crimes and disseminate unverified information through the social media. Earlier, a report from Ayorinde, Fausta and Ugochukwu (2020) revealed a significant relationship between youth restiveness and social media aggressive exposure.

Again, religion could have relationship with youth restiveness in Southwest, Nigeria. Though, in the time past, there have been sense of religious tolerance among the people of Southwest zone of Nigeria. However, in the recent time, religious intolerance seems to be gaining momentum in the zone. According to Elugbaju and Fagunwa (2023), the people in Southwest of Nigeria have enjoyed peaceful and harmonious co-existence in their various communities regardless of their religious affiliations. A study conducted by Fareo and Babale (2021) showed that religious

intolerance caused youth restiveness in Adamawa State, Northeast Nigeria.

More so, the state of security in Nigeria could have a connection with youth restiveness in Southwest Nigeria. Insecurity factors such as kidnapping, banditry, armed robbery, rape, and Fulani herders-farmers' clashes have continued to surface in Southwest in the recent time. These observed occurrences have caused a lot of staging of protest, showing of displeasure and dissatisfaction. According to Odeniyi and Shaibu (2024), the rising in the cases of kidnapping and other insecurity factors in Nigeria has made the youths in the North Central of Nigeria to embark on massive protest. Earlier, Ojobah, Chima and Emina (2020) had carried out a study in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State, where the respondents believed that insecurity led to youth restiveness in the Local Government Area.

However, it is noted that youth restiveness in Southwest, Nigeria has becoming devastating which demands urgent attention. It is equally felt that the identified social factors in Nigeria could have connection with youth restiveness in Southwest, Nigeria. Consequently, the study attempts to investigate the social factors and youth restiveness in Southwest, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Every individual needs peace to achieve goals in life. This peace would be attained when there is inner, psychological, emotional and physical calmness. Conversely, it appears that mutual understanding and relationship, even development, unity and peace are being replaced by hostility as a result of expression of anger, frustration, anxiety and violent demonstration or protest among the youths in Southwest, Nigeria since the eruption of year 2020 endsars protest in the six Southwest States of Nigeria.

Efforts have been made to discourage the surging of youth restiveness in Southwest, Nigeria. Youths have been made to acquire some entrepreneurial skills like tailoring, farming, confectionary making, barbing, etc. sponsored by both government and non-governmental institutions, restructuring of some government's agencies to advance the development and well-being of the youths. In spite of the above, there seems to be insignificant positive fruits in preventing youth restiveness in the zone.

Youth restiveness appears to have caused a lot of damages in the society. For instance, it has resulted into the loss of lives and properties, arrest and punishment of innocent individuals, social and economic strandedness, to mention just a few. Therefore, it is felt that youth restiveness may grow beyond taming if some of the associating social factors are not identified and lasting solutions found. Some of the assumed social factors include leadership, peer influence, social media, religion and state of security. Though, some researchers have delved into aspects of youth restiveness in Nigeria in terms of meaning, effects and challenges it poses on the socio-economic situation of Nigeria, it appears that little efforts have been made towards examining the social factors responsible for youth restiveness in Southwest, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

This study sought to investigate the relationship between social factors such as leadership, peer influence, social media, religion, state of security and youth restiveness in Southwest, Nigeria;

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between leadership and youth restiveness in Southwest, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant relationship between peer influence and youth restiveness in Southwest, Nigeria..
3. There is no significant relationship between social media and youth restiveness in Southwest, Nigeria..
4. There is no significant relationship between religion and youth restiveness in Southwest, Nigeria..
5. There is no significant relationship between state of security and youth restiveness in Southwest, Nigeria.

Methods

The descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. This method allowed the researcher to describe the facts and characteristics of existing situations of prevailing social factors and youth restiveness in Southwest, Nigeria.

The population for this study comprised all the youths who are between ages sixteen and thirty-five in Southwest, which comprises of

Ekiti, Lagos, Ogun, Ondo, Osun and Oyo States. in Nigeria.

The sample for this study consisted of 1166 youths in Southwest, Nigeria. Multistage sampling procedure was used to select the respondents. At the first stage, simple random sampling technique was used to select three States from among the six States that made up Southwest geo-political zone. At the second stage, proportionate random sampling technique was used to select Local Government Areas based on the available number of Local Government Areas in each of the selected States. The third stage involved the use of stratified random sampling technique to select communities within Local Government Areas, while at the fourth stage, the respondents were selected using simple random sampling techniques within towns and villages from Local Government Areas. Meanwhile, 1200 copies of the instrument were proportionally distributed among the selected States. 1166 copies were properly filled and retrieved. Consequently, 1166 respondents became the sample for the study.

A questionnaire tagged ‘Social Factors and Youth Restiveness’ (QSFLYR) was used to collect data for this study. The face and content validity were subjected to thorough screening by the experts in Social Studies Education, and Tests, Measurement and Evaluation in the Faculty of Education, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti. The experts determined the correctness and appropriateness of the instrument in making sure that it measures what it is purported to measure. The experts equally ascertained that the instrument contains the appropriate items that can actually elicit the intended responses on social factors and youth restiveness and also ensured that the items cover all the variables of the study.

The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha reliability testing method. In doing this, the copies of the questionnaire were administered on 50 respondents within the population but outside the sampled area. The overall reliability coefficient of 0.96 was obtained and this was considered high enough for this study. The instrument was administered on selected respondents in Southwest, Nigeria by the researchers with the help of six research assistants who assisted in the distribution and

retriever of the instrument from the respondents.

The data collected were analysed using inferential statistics. The hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis.

Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between leadership and youth restiveness.

Table 1: PPMC showing relationship between leadership and youth restiveness

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	r _{cal}	p-value
Leadership	1166	15.88	3.166	0.559*	0.000
Youth Restiveness	1166	68.82	8.977		

p < 0.05 (Significant Result)

It was discovered from the information in Table 1 that r_{cal} = 0.559; p = 0.000 < 0.05. Since the p value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implied that there was a significant relationship between leadership and youth restiveness.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between peer influence and youth restiveness.

Table 2: PPMC showing relationship between peer influence and youth restiveness

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	r _{cal}	p-value
Peer Influence	1166	11.39	3.979	0.271*	0.000
Youth Restiveness	1166	68.82	8.977		

p < 0.05 (Significant Result)

Table 2 showed that r_{cal} = 0.271; p = 0.000 < 0.05. Since the p value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implied that there was a significant relationship between peer influence and youth restiveness.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between social media and youth restiveness.

Table 3: PPMC showing relationship between social media and youth restiveness

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	r _{cal}	p-value
Social Media	1166	17.26	3.990	0.425*	0.000
Youth Restiveness	1166	68.82	8.977		

p < 0.05 (Significant Result)

Data in the Table 3 showed that r_{cal} = 0.425; p = 0.000 < 0.05. Since the p value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implied that there was a significant relationship between social media and youth restiveness.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant relationship between religion and youth restiveness.

Table 4: PPMC showing relationship between religion and youth restiveness

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	r _{cal}	p-value
Religion	1166	13.63	4.862	0.028	0.340
Youth Restiveness	1166	68.82	8.977		

p > 0.05 (Not Significant)

It was revealed from the information contained in Table 4 that r_{cal} = 0.028; p = 0.000 > 0.05.

Since the p value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis was not rejected. The implication of this is that, there was no significant relationship between religion and youth restiveness.

Hypothesis 5: There is no significant relationship between state of security and youth restiveness.

Table 5: PPMC showing relationship between state of security and youth restiveness

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	r_{cal}	p-value
State of Security	1166	15.04	3.687	0.393*	0.000
Youth Restiveness	1166	68.82	8.977		

p < 0.05 (Significant Result)

The information contained in Table 5 showed that $r_{cal} = 0.393$; $p = 0.000 < 0.05$. Since the p value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implied that there was a significant relationship between state of security and youth restiveness.

Discussion

The findings of this study showed that there was a significant relationship between leadership and youth restiveness. This indicates that leadership is one of the factors that contribute to restiveness among the youths. The reason may be that leadership approaches were not favourable. Favourable leadership approaches may likely discourage youth restiveness whilst unfavourable leadership approaches may give rise to youth restiveness. This is in conformity with Ugwu-Nwogo (2021) opinion that leadership approach has contributed to youth restiveness in Nigeria. The findings from the study also corroborated Tambawal and Sa'idu (2012) that youth restiveness was caused by leadership in northern Nigeria and Mba, Ihejirika and Deekor (2021) who found that poor leadership was responsible for youth restiveness in Andoni and Opobo/Nkoro Local Government Areas of Rivers State.

More so, this study found that there was a significant relationship between peer influence and youth restiveness. This implies that there is tendency for individual youths to lure or be lured into restiveness depending on the peers and associates. The reason for this may be on the fact that peers respect members' opinions and could communicate freely among one another. This is a consonance with Suleiman (2019) who submitted that youth restiveness was connected to peer influence among the youths. In the same vein, Uriah, Egbezor and Olorube (2014) found that youths influence

themselves to cause restiveness in Rivers State. More so, the finding also justified Zambuya (2022) who found that youth restiveness was motivated by peer influence.

This study also found that there was a significant relationship between social media and youth restiveness. This implies that social media like facebook, WhatsApp, newspapers, radio, television, may promote youth restiveness. This may be as a result of the dissemination and reception of unverified information and misrepresentation of ideas among the youths through different social media outlets. This finding supports Ezeji (2020) and Abraham (2020) who found that many youths spread rumours to commit crimes and violent behaviours through social media.

However, this study revealed that there was no significant relationship between religion and youth restiveness. This implies that youths' religious affiliations may not have a significant contribution on their possibility to engage in restiveness. This may be due to the culture that promotes religious tolerance, high level of education, and morality among the people of Southwest, Nigeria. This finding supported the assertion of Elugbaju and Faguwa (2023) that religious multiplicity has never been a problem among the people of Southwest of Nigeria. Conversely, Fareo and Babale (2021) found that religious intolerance contributed to youth restiveness in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

It was also revealed from the study that there was a significant relationship between the state of security and youth restiveness. This means that the state of security has connection to youth restiveness in Southwest, Nigeria. Therefore, lack of adequate security may have resulted into youth restiveness in Southwest, Nigeria. In consonance with this finding, Odeniyi and Shaibu (2024) reported that

insecurity factors like kidnapping and banditry have made the youths to stage protest in North Central of Nigeria. Again, this finding supports Ojobah, Chima and Emina (2020) who found that insecurity led to youth restiveness in Ogba/ Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Conclusion

Based on the findings from the study, it is concluded that leadership, peer influence, social media, drug abuse, state of security, contributed to youth restiveness in Southwest, Nigeria. It is further concluded that religion did not have connection with youth restiveness in Southwest Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. Leaders at various levels are encouraged to lead in accordance with moral principles and avoid the acts capable of creating problems in allocation and distribution of resources and political positions.
2. Parents and guardians are advised to give their children/wards proper orientation on the need to choose peer that will not influence or lure them into adopting negative behavior in the society.
3. Government at various levels and security agents are also encouraged to sincerely tackle insecurity in Southwest Nigeria and indeed Nigeria as a whole
4. Religious leaders should intensify efforts at propagating religious tolerance among the youths in Southwest, Nigeria
5. Government and agencies like Nigeria Broadcasting Commission (NBC) should ensure that media houses always adhere strictly to the conduct guiding broadcasting profession and that information dissemination on radio, and other social media outlets are to be properly scrutinized so as to get rid of misinformation capable of creating unnecessary tension in the society

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